

Complete Search Strategies

For Educational interventions for Shared Decision Making and the Role of Patient Agency: A Systematic Review

Ovid MEDLINE Search Strategy: 01/29/2020 – 1326

(exp *Patient Participation/ OR (shared decision making OR patient agency OR patient activation OR patient engagement OR patient participation or patient self efficacy).ab,ti.) AND (exp *Physicians/ OR exp *Nurses/ OR (physician* OR doctor OR doctors OR nurse* OR patient provider communication*).ab,ti.) AND ((intervention OR program OR programs OR training OR pilot study).ab,ti. OR interventions.ti.)

Embase search strategy: 01/29/2020 – 986 results

('shared decision making'/exp/mj OR 'patient activation'/exp OR 'patient activation measure'/exp OR 'patient engagement'/exp OR 'shared decision making':ab,ti OR 'patient agency':ab,ti OR 'patient activation':ab,ti OR 'patient engagement':ab,ti OR 'patient participation':ab,ti OR 'patient self efficacy':ab,ti) AND ('physician'/exp/mj OR 'nurse'/exp/mj OR physician*:ab,ti OR nurse*:ab,ti OR doctor:ab,ti OR doctors:ab,ti OR 'patient provider communication*':ab,ti) AND ('training'/exp/mj OR 'education program'/exp/mj OR intervention:ab,ti OR interventions:ti OR program:ab,ti OR programs:ab,ti OR training:ab,ti OR pilot-study:ab,ti) AND [english]/lim AND ([article]/lim OR [article in press]/lim OR [review]/lim) AND [2000-2020]/py

Web of Science, 01/28/2020 – 2,180 results

shared-decision-making OR patient -agency OR patient-activation OR patient-engagement OR
patient-participation OR patient-self-efficacy

physician* OR nurse* OR doctor OR doctors OR patient-provider-communication*

TOPIC box: (intervention OR program OR programs OR training OR pilot-study) OR TITLE

box: (interventions)

Limits: Language: English; Document Types: Article, Date: 2000-2020